

STUDIES IN FRIES MIGRATION. PART III. THE FRIES MIGRATION OF QUINOL ESTERS

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The Fries migration of various quinol esters, viz., quinol diacetate, dipropionate, di- and monobenzoates has been systematically studied for the first time. The effect of various factors such as the amount of anhydrous aluminium chloride, the reaction time, solvent and temperature on the course of the migration has been investigated. No migration could be effected unless the amount of aluminium chloride used was 3.3 mols. As a result, satisfactory method for preparation of quinacetophenone and quinpropionophenone, otherwise obtained in poor yields, has been evolved. In case of quinol dibenzoate, the reaction becomes complicated as the temperature at which the migration is carried out, is increased, and besides the main product, 2-hydroxy-5-benzoyloxybenzophenone, several other products are formed. In no case a diketone was isolated.

The work described in the previous parts of this series (Thakor and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 199, 234) mainly concerned the Fries migration in the coumarin derivatives. In the present investigation, it has been extended to various quinol esters; quinol diacetate, dipropionate and mono- and di-benzoates have been investigated.

No systematic work has been done so far to study the Fries migration of quinol esters. It has been reported that quinol diacetate does not undergo the Fries transformation under the usual experimental conditions (Heller, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2389; Mauthner, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1934, ii, 139, 293). However, Rosenmund and Lohfert (*Ber.*, 1928, 61, 2602) and recently Desai and Mavani (*Curr. Sci.*, 1941, 10, 524) and Shahane (*ibid.*, p. 523) have reported that the above migration is possible under certain conditions. The higher quinol esters like quinol distearate, 4-methoxyphenyl palmitate and stearate do not undergo this migration (Cook, Heilbron and Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 659; Cruickshank and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1938, 2064). Incidentally it may be noted that the diacetate of 2-methoxyquinol smoothly migrates yielding the expected product, 2:5-dihydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (Mauthner, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1933, ii, 136, 205), whereas quinol itself does not undergo the Friedel-Crafts or Hoesch reaction; it reacts under the conditions of the Nencki reaction yielding quinacetophenone in a poor yield (Nencki and Schmid, *ibid.*, 1881, ii, 23, 546). Russel and Clarke (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2654) obtained a slightly better yield (20-25%) by a modified Nencki procedure.

In the present work, we have investigated the effect of various factors on the course of the Fries migration of quinol diacetate. For the sake of brevity, the results of various experiments under different conditions are presented in a tabular form (Table I). It has led us to evolve the best conditions for the preparation of quinacetophenone (II, R=Me) from quinol diacetate (I, R=Me) in good yield.

TABLE I

Fries migration of quinol diacetate

Quinol diacetate used in each experiment = 5 g.

Expt. No.	Temp.	Time.	Amount of AlCl_3 .	Products	
				Unchanged quinol diacetate.	Quinacetophenone.
1	85°-90°	4 hours	3.3 M	3.0 g.	...
2	120°-130°	4	3.3	2.5	0.5 g.
3	140°-160°	4	3.3	...	2.7
4	"	1	3.3	...	2.2
5	"	4	3.3 (60 c.c. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$)	...	...
6	"	4	3.3 (30 c.c. CS_2 for mixing)	...	2.1
7	"	4	2.2 M	2.5	...
8	"	4	1.1	3.1	...
9	"	4	5.5	...	2.7
10	170°-180°	4	3.3	...	1.5
11	"	4	2.2	2.2	Trace
12	"	1	3.3	...	1.3
13	20°-25°	24	3.3 (60 c.c. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$)	...	...

- (1) All the experiments recorded here were repeated several times and concordant results were obtained.
- (2) In all the experiments after the products were separated, a small quantity of a black tarry material was always left behind. It could not be purified.

The same conditions (the temperature has to be carefully regulated to 140°) were also found to be applicable in the case of migration of quinol dipropionate (I, R = Et).

The Fries migration of benzoyl esters of quinol has practically remained uninvestigated. By analogy with quinol diacetate and dipropionate, the migration of quinol dibenzoate was expected to yield quinbenzophenone. The expectation was not realised ;

instead of quinbenzophenone, however, it afforded a product of m. p. 94° - 95° accompanied with the original dibenzoate. The product has been identified to be 2-hydroxy-5-benzoyloxybenzophenone (III, $R=COPh$; $R_1=Ph$) on the following considerations: (i) It is soluble in alkali indicating free $-OH$ group and further, it gives ferric chloride colour test indicating $-OH$ and $-COPh$ groups in *ortho* positions; (ii) its benzoyl derivative has the same melting point as the dibenzoyl derivative of quinbenzophenone, the mixed melting point with an authentic sample remaining unchanged; (iii) on hydrolysis by concentrated sulphuric acid, quinbenzophenone was produced (Bogert and Howells, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 840; cf. Klinger and Standke, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 1340).

In course of the further work, it has been found that 2-hydroxy-5-benzoyloxybenzophenone is the main product of the reaction. For the sake of brevity, the results of all the experiments under different conditions are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Fries migration of quinol dibenzoate

Quinol dibenzoate used in each experiment = 3 g.

Exp. No.	Temp.	Time.	Amount of $AlCl_3$.	Quinol dibenzoate.	Monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone.	Quinol monobenzoate.
1	120°	1 hr	3.3M	2.2 g.	Trace	...
2	120°	4	3.3	1.9	Trace	...
3	140°	3	3.3	1.2	0.3 g.	...
4	140°	4	3.3 + 1.1 g. quinol	0.6	...	...
5	140°	4	3.3 + 0.6 g. quinol	1.0	Trace	0.2 g.
6	140°	1	3.3	0.3	1.0 g.	...
7	140°	3	3.3 + 40 c.c. $C_6H_5NO_2$	...	...	...
8	20° - 25° (room temp.)	24	3.3 + 40 c.c. $C_6H_5NO_2$	1.2	...	...
9	140°	1	1.1M	2.5	...	...
10	140°	1	2.2	2.3	...	...
11	140°	1	5.5	0.3	1.0 g.	...
12	150° - 155°	3	3.3	0.4	0.4	0.4 g.
13	180°	1	3.3	0.2	0.3	0.3
14	200° - 205°	1	3.3	0.2	0.2	0.4
15	„	1	5.5	0.2	0.2	0.3

- (1) In the experiments 13, 14 and 15, 0.3 g. of quinbenzophenone was isolated, in addition to the products mentioned.
- (2) In experiments 8, 13 and 14, traces of quinol were obtained from ether extracts of the mother-liquor after other products were separated off.
- (3) In experiment 7, no definite product could be isolated, only charred mass was produced.

It will be seen that the migration becomes complex as the temperature is raised. At 180° a small quantity of quinbenzophenone along with the other products is isolated. At higher temperature, much pasty mass is obtained. It is noteworthy that the reaction is not simple migration at higher temperatures. Besides, monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone, quinol monobenzoate, quinbenzophenone, quinol and its dibenzoate are among the other products which have been isolated. Incidentally, it may be mentioned that in no case a diketone was isolated.

The migration of quinol monobenzoate was expected to produce quinbenzophenone in good yield, but actually the migration was found complicated. Here also, 2-hydroxy-5-benzoyloxybenzophenone was found to be the main product. However, in all cases quinol dibenzoate was isolated in appreciable quantity. In no case, either quinbenzophenone or a diketone could be isolated. The results of the various experiments are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Fries migration of quinol monobenzoate

Quinol monobenzoate used in each experiment = 2.1 g. Amount of AlCl₃ used in each experiment = 4.4 g. (3.3 mols).

Exp. No.	Temp.	Time.	Quinol dibenzoate.	Monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone.	Quinol monobenzoate.
1	120°	1 hr.	0.3 g.	...	0.6 g.
2	120°	4	0.3	...	0.4
3	140°	1	0.4	0.3g.	0.2
4	140°	4	0.4	0.2	0.2
5	160°-170°	1	0.2	0.1	Trace
6	200°	1	0.1	...	...

In all experiments a variable amount of blackish residue remained after isolation of the different crystalline products.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of Quinol Esters

Quinol diacetate was prepared by the following method which gave a satisfactory yield. Acetic anhydride (102 g., 2 M) was gradually added to the solution of quinol (55 g., 1.0 M) in sodium carbonate solution (110 g. in 1650 c. c. water) over a period of half an hour. The mixture was mechanically stirred all the while. After the addition was over, the precipitated diacetate was allowed to settle. It was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 123-24°, yield 78-80 g.

Quinol Dipropionate.—Propionic anhydride (19.5 g., 1.5 M), followed by ice (about 50 g.), was quickly added to the solution of quinol (11 g., 1 M) in 60% sodium hydroxide solution (10 c. c.). The solid that immediately separated, was collected and crystallised from alcohol in thin, lustrous plates, m. p. 112-13°, yield 15-16 g.

Quinol dibenzoate was prepared by the usual Schotten-Baumann method, m. p. 200-201°.

Quinol monobenzoate was prepared according to the method of Witt and Johnson (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1908), m. p. 162-63°. A small quantity of quinol dibenzoate was also obtained as alcohol-insoluble residue.

The Fries migrations of the different esters were carried out by the same general method described in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 201).

Preparative Method for Quinacetophenone.—An intimate mixture of quinol diacetate (50 g.) and aluminium chloride (110 g.) was heated at 140°-160° for 4 hours. After decomposing the reaction mixture by ice and hydrochloric acid, the solid was collected and crystallised from alcohol in greenish needles, m. p. 201°-202°, yield 25-30 g.

Fries Migration of Quinol Dipropionate.—The ester (25 g.) and aluminium chloride (50 g.) were intimately mixed and heated for 4 hours at 130°-140°. The product was decomposed by ice and hydrochloric acid and the solid after filtration was crystallised from hot water in fine needles, m. p. 91-92°, yield 14 g.

*Isolation of the different Products from the Migration mixture of
Quinol Dibenzoate*

Experiment No. 13 in Table II is described in details as a typical experiment.

The mixture of aluminium chloride and ester was heated as outlined in the general method. The solid obtained on decomposition of the reaction mixture was extracted with hot water. The aqueous solution (A) and the residue (B) were separately examined.

(A). The aqueous extract on cooling deposited needles, m. p. 110-20°. The needles were redissolved in boiling water and allowed to cool to about 75°-80°. The crystals separating were filtered off and recrystallised from water, m. p. 162-63° (small quantity). It was identified as quinol monobenzoate by the mixed melting point with an authentic sample. The filtrate on further cooling gave flat needles, which on recrystallisation melted at 124-25°. The product was identified as quinbenzophenone. (Found : C, 72.51 ; H, 4.62. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$: C, 72.9 ; H, 4.67 per cent).

Quinbenzophenone is soluble in sodium hydroxide and concentrated sulphuric acid with dark red colour and gives dark green colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. It is soluble in all common solvents and hot water. It reduces ammoniacal silver nitrate and Fehling's solution.

The mother-liquor, after separation of quinol monobenzoate and quinbenzophenone, gave on extraction with ether brown residue containing some white needles. Some of the needles were picked up and identified as quinol, m. p. 169-70° (mixed m. p. with a Merck's sample).

(B). The insoluble residue was extracted with alcohol. The alcoholic extract gave greenish yellow needles, m. p. 94-95°, which were identified as monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone. (Found : C, 75.61 ; H, 4.46. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 75.47 ; H, 4.4 per cent).

Monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone is soluble in all common organic solvents but insoluble in hot water. It dissolves in sodium hydroxide with deep red colour. With alcoholic ferric chloride it gives a dark green coloration.

The mother-liquor, after separation of monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone, was diluted and the brown solid obtained was crystallised from water, m. p. 162-63°. It was quinol monobenzoate.

The insoluble alcoholic residue after crystallisation from acetic acid was found to be quinol dibenzoate, m. p. 200°-201°.

The *acetyl derivative* of monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone was prepared by sodium acetate method and crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 94-95°. The mixed melting point with the original ketone was depressed to 76-78°. (Found : C, 72.81 ; H, 4.58. $C_{22}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.33 ; H, 4.44 per cent).

The *benzoyl derivative*, prepared by Schotten-Baumann method, melted at 117-18° (mixed m. p. with the dibenzoyl derivative of quinbenzophenone). (Found : C, 76.56 ; H, 4.10. $C_{27}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 76.77 ; H, 4.26 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone.—The ketone (1 g.) was kept overnight with concentrated sulphuric acid (5 to 7 c.c.). The deep red mixture was poured on ice and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from hot water, m. p. 124-25° (mixed m. p. with quinbenzophenone).

The *dibenzoate*, derived from quinbenzophenone by Schotten-Baumann, was prepared by the usual method, m. p. at 117-18°.

The *semicarbazone*, prepared by the usual method, melted at 159-60° (decomp.).

The *dimethoxy* derivative, prepared by means of dimethyl sulphate, crystallised from petrol, m. p. 51-52°. Kaufmann and Grombach (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 796) give the same melting point.

DISCUSSION

It will be seen from the result that the amount of aluminium chloride required for migration is three mols. without which no migration is possible. With less than three mols. of aluminium chloride, no migration product could be isolated, unchanged ester or pasty mass was obtained. Even at higher temperature, the less amount of aluminium chloride did not promote the reaction. Large quantity of aluminium chloride (5.5 mols.) did not affect either the yield or the course of the reaction.

Aluminium chloride has a tendency to form complexes with compounds containing oxygen atoms ; it appears that the extra two mols. are utilized in the complex formation with the hydroxy-ester groups of quinol. Such ester complexes have been actually isolated as intermediate products in many reactions (Gaustavson, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1880, ii, 34, 322 ; Perrier, *ibid.*, 1893, iii, 9, 1049 ; Walker and Spencer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 83, 1108).

The effect of temperature is important. As the *para* position is occupied, the only possibility is of the *ortho* migration. In no case the migration was observed below 140°. Quinol diacetate on migration yields always quinbenzophenone ; in case of dibenzoate and monobenzoate, 2-hydroxy-5-benzoyloxybenzophenone is formed, one of the

two ester groups remaining unaffected. With increase in temperature, yield of quinacetophenone is lowered; while in the case of benzoyl ester, the reaction becomes complicated and quinol monobenzoate, quinol and quinbenzophenone are produced along with the diminishing yield of 2-hydroxy-5-benzoyloxybenzophenone. The other products may be due to the hydrolysis of the previously formed products at higher temperatures. The presence of quinol dibenzoate even at higher temperatures is interesting. It shows that either the reaction is incomplete or it is formed during the course of the reaction; it shows that it is an intramolecular reaction, since in the migration of quinol monobenzoate, it is invariably isolated. Even when the quantity of aluminium chloride is in large excess (5.5 mols.) and the temperature as high as 200°, quinol dibenzoate is invariably isolated as one of the products. In case of quinol monobenzoate, the material is charred at higher temperatures, but no quinbenzophenone is formed.

In the present work nitrobenzene as a solvent was found to have no beneficial effect but rather it retarded the reaction. This is in contrast to its beneficial effect in many of the migrations studied previously.

It is apparent that the nature of the group plays an important part. The migration of quinol diacetate leads to the dihydroxy ketonic compound, but in case of quinol dibenzoate, one of the two benzoyl groups is firmly held. This is in accord with the view that an aromatic acid residue is more tenaciously held up by the oxygen atom of the phenol molecule than an aliphatic one (Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 460, 56). At higher temperature, quinol and quinbenzophenone are formed, but it may be due to the effect of temperature or side reactions. In case of quinol diacetate, no monoacetoxy ketone could be isolated, due to the migration and hydrolysis having taken place simultaneously.

Earlier workers in this field used to prolong the reaction for a very long time, but recently Rosenmund and Schnurr (*loc. cit.*) observed that actually the reaction was over within 15 to 20 minutes. In the present case, the reaction is almost over in the first hour after which the evolution of hydrochloric acid gas slackens. The continuation of heating for a longer period does not increase the yield of quinacetophenone, while in the case of dibenzoate, it is not appreciable as the amount of the product is neither substantially lowered or increased. However, it only increases the amount of pasty residue in the latter case.

From the above discussion, optimum conditions for the migration of quinol diacetate are those given in experiment 3 in Table I and for dibenzoate and monobenzoate are those given in experiments 6 and 3 of Table II and III respectively. These optimum conditions are applicable for the large-scale migration of quinol diacetate and dipropionate but are of no avail in the case of benzoyl esters. With large quantities of the latter esters, the yield of the migrated product is not increased in the same ratio. The suitable method for the preparation of quinbenzophenone appears to be the hydrolysis of monobenzoyl quinbenzophenone, easily obtained by the migration of quinol mono or dibenzoates.